

Responses to drought and desertification in the Moroccan Draa Valley: resilience at the expense of sustainability?

ABSTRACT

Dryland and oasis communities in developing countries are considered to be among the most threatened by climate change impacts and the consequences of increasing human pressure on the environment. For centuries nomads and oasis communities have been demonstrating their adaptive capacities and resilience by coping with tough environmental conditions. In the Moroccan Drâa Valley, we explore different top-down, bottom-up, regional, local and autonomous adaptations strategies applied in response to increasing droughts and desertification rates. The adaptations of different sectors and actors have been integrated in a regional study in order to frame them from the resilience and sustainability perspectives. The findings underline that while human adaptive strategies are mostly capable of addressing stressors and enhancing resilience (in the short run) locally, ecosystems resilience and regional social-ecological sustainability are under threat. The paper concludes by underlining the importance of reframing resilient strategies in the light of sustainability and long term resilience perspectives.

Key words: Resilience, Sustainability, Drought, Desertification, Dryland, DESERTEC, Morocco, Draa Valley, Maladaptation

1. On droughts adaptations and desertification in dryland

Dryland areas cover more than 40% of the Earth's land surface (Oldeman et al. 1990) hosting more than 2 billion inhabitants (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment 2005) who may suffer the adverse effects of climate change (CC). In the near future, an increase in temperature is more likely in summer whereas less likely in winter time, as well as there will be an increase in length, intensity, and frequency of warm spells or heat waves (IPCC, 2013). This scenario will lead to increasing social and ecological vulnerability, provoking potential losses of soil fertility, lower livestock productivity, alterations in pest and disease risks, habitat changes and reduced availability of water in already water scarce regions (Schulz and Judex 2008). These impacts, combined with increasing drought severity, represent a significant concern, which can be further exacerbated by human actions, contributing to what can be seen as the social-ecological deadline for life in dryland areas: landscape desertification.

The concept of desertification emerged during the first colonisation of West Africa (Stebbing 1935) and from the study of droughts and their recovery in the Sahel. This constituted the scientific basis to launch the desertification issue and debates in the political arena during the United Nations Conference on Desertification (UNCOD), held in Nairobi in 1977. Today, desertification is a worldwide problem affecting 250 million people (UNCCD 2003) and hundreds of definitions have been framed within different contexts (Glantz and Orlovsky 1983). Notwithstanding the debate over the evolution of the term (Herrmann and Hutchinson 2005), we can consider desertification as an irreversible environmental crisis in which land becomes sterile (Mainguet 1995). While drought is a climate induced phenomenon (Kallis 2008), desertification is a soil degradation process caused by synergistic climate and human land management (Nicholson et al. 1998). As Spooner pointed out, desertification is a social (human induced) problem (Spooner 1987); this is why at least one third of the present global deserts are a result of unsustainable land use (UNEP 1991).

In fragile social-ecological systems, human activities can negatively affect ecological processes and resilience (Salt and Walker 2006), such as the robustness to withstand and the capacity to recover from crisis. Furthermore, reduction in availability of resources can lead society to increase the pressure on these resources because of autonomous unsustainable adaptations (Adger et al. 2011). Observations from dryland contexts confirm that ecological resilience is reduced after each severe drought, especially if the drought occurs simultaneously with population growth (Mainguet and Silva 1998). This is confirmed in this case study in which urban sprawl, population growth and abandoning rural land are direct consequences of adaptations to environmental crisis and increasing water scarcity. Both autonomous adaptations and top-down institutional plans act mainly within short term strategies in order to maximize temporal social benefits, while less concern is paid to ecological dynamics and consequences. In so doing,

desertification rates increase because integrated (spatial, social, temporal) approaches are not taken in response to the crisis.

This paper seeks to explore the relationship between adaptation measures at different scales, ecological resilience, and the sustainability long term patterns of the Draa Valley. Three years of fieldwork, conducted between 2010 and 2012 along the Moroccan region, contributed to build the empirical basis supporting the paper main statements, stressing the need to reframe and coordinate adaptation measures between scales, and social and ecological domains. Qualitative sociological survey methods (random sampling, structured and unstructured questionnaires and interviews with key stakeholders or institution representatives) were used and incorporated a multidisciplinary range of English, French and Arab literature.

2. Introduction to the Drâa Valley study area and the resilience of its ancient social-ecological system.

The Drâa Valley (UNESCO biosphere reserve) is part of the most important river basin of the Southeastern part of Morocco (Fig 1) because of its chain of oases that run from the High Atlas Mountains toward the Saharan desert. The Drâa River was the largest Moroccan river before a dam was constructed, controlling its water flows and reducing its length. Along the river's course, the average annual rainfall registers around 300 mm/y in the High Atlas Mountains, 200 mm/y in the valleys and just 60 mm/year or less from Zagora to the southern oasis (FAO 2006). Evaporation ranges between 2000 and 3,000 mm per year (Tazi 2008) while violent, hot and dry winds accentuate the salt concentration in the soil by increasing the evapotranspiration.

- Insert Fig 1.

Despite the scarce rainfall and high evaporation rates, the valley has been recognized for its agricultural richness and fertile soils that nomads used for date production, which they exchanged with silver and other precious products (BioNomad 2008) at the Timbuktu market (the most important ancient Western African market).

Historically, the farming sector within the oases was a hierarchic multilayer system (Fauozi 1986). A dense network of irrigation channels allowed water to flow from the higher and larger channels (from which date palms received water first) into the smaller ones (for cereals and other crops). Palm trees provided oases with the necessary microclimate for agriculture while the periodic floods brought essential sediments and nutrients to enhance the soil fertility.

For centuries those valley populations demonstrated their resilience thanks to a deep environmental knowledge (Casciarri 2003) and respect for environmental thresholds (population growth, moves, lands uses), a mutual and hierarchic approach to common resources management (Davis 2005), and their flexible

lifestyles (temporal migrations to towns in case of drought and multi-incomes organization within each family). The limited availability of resources and the temporal droughts were not a threat to the survival of the *Draoui* (Drâa Valley population in Arab) (Beaumont 1989).

3. **Social and climatic drivers of change and related impacts: a comprehensive understanding of increasing regional vulnerability patterns**

3.1 Climate change and desertification: synergies between climatic and human induced impacts

According to the PACC project¹, by the year 2050, oases (including the Draa Valley) will experience a reduction from 10 to 40% of the cumulative rainfall during the winter, a 30% decrease in the number of wet and rainy days and an increase in temperatures from 1-3.2°C (Maroc, 2011). The IPCC has confirmed such trends expecting a decrease of 20-30% in rainfall and a 2.5 to 5C° increasing air temperatures by the year 2080 (IPCC 2007).

Touchan et al. (2008) analyzed the period from 1456 to 2002 identifying an average of 16 drought episodes per century. Traditional Draoua knowledge indicates that for every seven good years, there are seven hard years (“*saba’ shina wa saba’ zina*“) referring to the natural equilibrium between droughts and rainy seasons. For the 1912 to 1992 period, an average interval between droughts of only three years was found (Swearingen 1992). Adaptive capacities of the Draoua population lay in their flexible lifestyle, migrating temporarily, for example, during drought crisis. This strategy has changed since 1972 and the building of a huge dam upstream (see Fig 2, Ouarzazate water reservoir) and at the same time three between the most severe droughts happened during the periods 1980 to 1986 and from 1991 to 1995. These recent dry periods are reported in Tab 1 (Ministere de l’Energie, des Mines, de l’Eau et de l’Environnement, Departament de l’Eau, 2012).

- Insert Fig 2.

Beginning in 1972, the signs of a serious regional environmental crisis started to appear. Because of the droughts and dam water retention, almost half of the trees in the date palm areas in the southern foothills of the High Atlas mountains died, resulting in a reduction from 4575 km² to just 1342 km² (MEMEE, 2001; Ben Mohammadi 2000). Furthermore, as palm trees constitute the core element for the oasis agriculture (and animals fodder crops are usually produced within the palm groves) the number of animals also dropped because of both water and

¹ Projet Adaptation au Changement Climatique au Maroc pour des Oasis Résilientes

fodder unavailability² (Heidecke and Roth 2008; Ait Hamza et al. 2009). Tab.1 illustrates the relationship between precipitations (inflow water into the upstream dam reservoir), outflow waters from the dam and animals fluctuations in numbers and species along the entire Valley. While mules per farmer number remained stable, the majority of the animals were lost, sold, became ill or were eaten (Schulz and Judex 2008).

- Insert Tab 1.

The environmental crisis resulted in a reduction in the traditional oasis life style and land management practices and an increase in urbanization (Davis 2005; Platt 2008). Other challenges that the oasis faces include periodical locust invasions and wind erosion, considered to be the major driver of soil silting (silting covers 30.000 hectares just in the provinces of Ouarzazate and Zagora) (Maroc 2001). Erosion along the Drâa has been estimated to average 5.8 m³/ha/year (Ben Mohammadi 2000). Combined with land-uses and unsustainable water management practices, such as the exploitation of sandy soils (Benmohammadi 2000) and uncontrolled firewood collection (Mainguet 1979), these oases are increasingly vulnerable and the desertification process is being enhanced.

3.2 Humans drivers and the unsustainable patterns of growth: command and control practices.

As the oasis chain, its microclimate and its groundwater reservoirs play an essential role as natural barrier against desertification (Maroc 2009a), any humans alteration of such ecosystem functioning (or any overexploitation of the relative ecosystem services) considerably accelerates the desertification processes (Davis 2006).

The Draa river flow is nowadays entirely controlled by the Mansur Al-Dahbi dam (Ouarzazate, Fig 2), which was built in 1972 to control flood risks and assure regular water flows for irrigation along the valley. The dam also generates hydroelectric energy for Rabat. An exhaustive list of scientific literature explores the environmental impacts of the dam, the most relevant being: the drying up of the downstream groundwater table, loss of soil fertility due to the sediments retention behind the dam (Ait Hamza et al. 2009), the drying up of the lake Iriki (see Fig 2) (BioNomaD 2008) and the consequent increasing soil and ground water salinity. Salinity reached the level of 4 mmhos / cm, increasing from 17.4% in Mezguita to 48% in M'hamid (Zainabi 2003). Other indirect impacts resulted from farmers (groups) autonomous adaptation practices such as increasing groundwater pumping (Heidecke et al. 2010) and the new agricultural system (and new market based crops) that this centralized water management encouraged.

² In the last years (2008-2012) the prices of animal feed were up between 20% and 40%, with a simultaneous fall in prices of livestock between 30% and 50 % (Office Régional de Mise en Valeur Agricole d'Ouarzazate 2012)

New cropping practices are in conflict with traditional ways (Tazi 2008). While southern oases suffered the consequences of centralized water management (increasing saltwater and desertification process, lack of freshwater along canals etc), northern oases were benefitting from opportunities offered by new local markets (mainly tourism and agricultural production for exportation) to serve global commodities chains (Davis 2005; WaterGov 2012). Such (short term) opportunities expanded at the expense of natural resources and involved the intensive use of flood irrigation techniques (with high water losses).

A second unsustainable human driver of resource overexploitation started with Ouarzazate opening its arms to the movie industry in 1962 (with the building of Atlas studios) thereby increasing tourism and foreign markets based income and dependency. The urbanization process accelerated when the Sand War in 1963 (between Morocco and Algeria for southern borders) prevented nomads from accessing essential grazing lands and forced them into settlements (Casciarri 2003). Urbanization was enhanced further by the 1976 decentralization policy, which aimed to confer more power to communal districts. For this reason, urban centres have developed faster than the rural areas (0.8 % average annual growth) and the four towns of Ouarzazate, Tabount, Zagora and Tinerhir (Fig 2) contain 77.6 % of the urban valley population (Zainabi 2003). Impacts of this urbanization are visible both in the land abandoning process along the valley and high water consumption rates of some new market sectors. An increase in the water consumption rates in urban areas by the tourist sector have seen Zagora's water use rise from 15,967 m³ (4% of the total water uses) in 1982 to 89,575 m³ (13%) in 2000, which means an increase of 461% (Zainabi 2003; Ministère de Tourisme, 2011). The water consumption rates of new crops for exportation confirm the increasing impact derived from this second human driver of local change. These factors are pushing a transition from a traditional (environmental and ecosystem functioning knowledge) society, with common and participative resource management practices, to a society dependent on external markets (not participative, nor resilient, but top-down and environmentally unsustainable) (Zainabi 2003; Casciarri 2003; Davis 2005).

4. Reviewing different adaptation strategies and impacts responses

In this section we explore in depth, at the regional scale, the degree of sustainability of the local (or sectors) CC adaptation strategies. The material navigates both the top down policies and the complex autonomous local adaptations influencing cross scales dynamics. Although social resilience is expressed in the short term by almost all the adaptations strategies, middle and long term resilience (and so sustainability) is most threatened by the synergistic cross scale effects of the adopted choices.

4.1 The links between renewable energy, water consumption and increasing desertification

In 2010 the king of Morocco introduced the new Moroccan Renewable Energy Plan with the aim to install five solar power plants before 2020, with a total capacity of 2000 Megawatts (Mw) and a cost of around Euro 7 billions (Maroc 2010; Konate et al. 2012). These power plants will meet the country's CC mitigation policy aims, reduce dependency on the import of energy and support the growing demand for electricity supply not only for Morocco, but also for other Middle Eastern (Emirates) and North African (MENA) countries. This national renewable energy project is connected to a bigger long-term international cooperation project, called DESERTEC and which includes Europe (Germany) and the MENA region. The final aim of this macro project would be to produce both clean energy in a centralized way from desert solar power (Bakkoury 2010) and desalinated water, addressing the demand of two thirds of the MENA region. Finally, another 15% of the energy would be sold and transported to Europe by Direct Current High Voltage, which would lose a low 10-15% of energy during transmission (The Club of Rome 2011). The first solar power plant, of 500 Mw, was planned to cover an area of 2.500 ha just 10 km from Ouarzazate. Due to recent financial problems, a solar thermal parabolic plant with a capacity of just 160 Mw³ began construction in 2010 (Bunderministerium fur Umwelt, Naturschutz und Reaktorsicherheit 2011). This project has an estimated cost of around 1042,32 million Euros (Konate et al. 2012). According to interviews and official reports, it should address the energy needs of the 300,000 people in the Ouarzazate province, currently dependent on firewood, thereby reducing the human pressures on vegetation.

Despite the benefits of CC mitigation and the provision of renewable energy, social resilience could be reduced as a result of an increased dependency on the project to provide energy at market prices. From a social resilience perspective, not only will this dependency result in a loss of the ability to adapt and deal with environmental crises such as droughts, but the population would have no control over their energy production. Centralized structures are less resilient than distributed or decentralized systems, with regard to natural hazards (Baran 1964). This centralized plant will have a high cost in terms of water withdrawal from the Ouarzazate water reservoir to run its "humid" cooling system. The amount of water has been estimated to be between 2 and 5Mm³/year (Konate et al. 2012, Drâa Water Basin Authority interviews).

Considering the current environmental crisis in the southern oases, CC predictions (section 3.1) and the outputs of numerous interviews, we believe that creating and linking new consumers (previously dependent on firewood for energy) to a centralized solar plant which requires significant amounts of water, is not the most resilient, nor sustainable option. On the contrary, it would contribute to the desertification of the southern oases by increasing water consumption upstream. Furthermore, the average price for solar power energy production is

³ This first central is financed by the German Federal Environment Ministry in coordination with the World Bank, the African Development Bank, the European Investment Bank, the French Development Bank and The European Commission

currently 22 Euro cents/Kw, while the Moroccan subsidized price for energy is equivalent to 4 cents/Kw (Stern journal 2012). Photovoltaic energy production would cost 20 cents/Kw and it would be a cheaper and a more resilient option (because based on a distributive network, and because people would be directly involved in the control of the energy production). It would also be more sustainable because the system does not require water. Furthermore, its implementation could be gradual over time thereby reducing the immediate investment cost.

4.2 Water management: centralized or decentralized?

After the dramatic droughts in the '80s and '90s, the 1995 Water law, *Loi sur l'Eau*, introduced the new principal national legal water framework, recognizing that all water resources are public goods and that they should be managed at river basin level (Maroc 1995). This law introduces new *redevance de bassin* (basin charge) taxes, based on water withdrawal and pollution, as exceptional power to the administration for dealing with droughts⁴. Unfortunately, the river basin master plan designed by the River Basin Agency of Souss-Massa Draa is still not approved (year 2012) although more than seventeen years have passed, highlighting the difficulties of the implementation of this integrated water resources management framework (Jeffrey and Gearey 2006; Lankford and Cour 2005; Biwas 2004).

In contrast to the decentralized water management aims of the Water Law, the Moroccan government has already planned the construction of a new dam called *Tiouine*, upstream from Ouarzazate (see FIG 3). It is under construction (it should be completed by 2014) and will store up to 273 Mm³ water according to the head of the Souss-Massa-Draa River Basin Agency interview, although other sources indicate that the capacity will be 100 Mm³ of water (Monje et al. 2011; Bravo and Ybern 2008). Water impounded by the new dam will be used in response to the increasing urban demand for drinkable water in Ouarzazate as a result of the decreasing water quality from the old Mansour Al-Dhabi dam, which is suffering from high sedimentation rates. Our interviews suggest that although the water quality issue would be solved in the short term, this second dam will most likely suffer the same middle term efficiency failure of the first one due to high sediment accumulation and high evaporation rates⁵.

- Insert Fig 3

⁴ In the case of severe drought, a decree demarcates the area where the administration receives such powers that allow exceptional and temporal diminution in surface water abstraction, and requiring the use of underground resources (Ouassou et al. 2005)

⁵ Mansour Al-Dhabi water reservoir currently loses 16 Mm³/year from surface water evaporation, while just 5 Mm³ of water is required to meet the annual demand for Ouarzazate.

4.3 Autonomous short-term unsustainable adaptations to droughts and their cross scales effects.

An example of the autonomous short term adaptations to droughts and their cross scales effects is the shift from surface to groundwater irrigation that occurred during and after the most severe droughts of the '90s. Water for irrigation was not released from the upstream dam continuously⁶. The water distribution strategy for the six oases allocates water to the downstream oases first (Faouzi 1986), causing the upstream oases to be severely affected by the droughts (Outabhit 1992). In response to the shortage of water, farmers began pumping groundwater from their private wells. This response to the situation provoked an unsustainable chain effect and the number of water pumps increased from 2.000 in 1977, to 4.000 in 1985 (Faouzi 1986), nearly 7.000 in 2005 (Ait Hamza et al. 2009) and more than 10.000 in 2011 (interviews, 2011-2012). The downstream oases were the first to suffer from the uncontrolled extraction of groundwater upstream which resulted in soil and groundwater salinization (Casciarri 2003).

In addition to the cross scale effects on groundwater and the unsustainable autonomous reaction to droughts, further accelerating the crisis in the southern oases is the emergence of new foreign agricultural markets. These markets favoured farmers owning the deeper wells because crops requiring more water could be grown. For example, after the '80s *Bayoud* disease outbreak, a palm tree illness caused by drought, the oasis space dedicated to date production decreased by 34% (Maroc 2010) and a watermelon crop market emerged as a very profitable alternative. Watermelon fields increased from just 150 ha to more than 650 ha in the last 2 years (Tab 2). Neither the old irrigation system, nor modern motor-pumps, can satisfy the water demands of the southern farmers caused by the uncontrolled and unintegrated water uses along the valley (Rademacher 2008), documenting the ecological concerns related to increased irrigation water needs.

Insert Table 2

4.4 New directions in saving valley agriculture

The new national agriculture programme released in 2008 aimed to reduce the dependence of the country on cereal imports and to abate the exodus of people from rural areas (Maroc 2008a; Lybbert et al. 2009). The plan *Maroc Vert* (green Morocco) was built around two key aims. The first aimed to maximize the output from intensive agriculture (Badraoui et al. 2000; Davis 2006) fostering production

⁶ The amount of released water, to be divided between the six oasis reservoirs, is discussed in a yearly meeting between different local institutions, however there is no clear rule as to how this water is distributed. The six annual discharges of the dam in 1973 (the minimum for a satisfying the Valley agricultural cycle) diminished to 4 and until its ecologically unsustainable minimum released during 2002–3 (2 times less water than the 40million of m³ necessary to recover the groundwater system). See also Tab. 1.

techniques, extension of cropland, improvement of localized irrigation techniques and an improved processing of agricultural products (Maroc 2008a). The second objective was to fight poverty by improving the socio-economic impacts of investments directed at small farmers. Almost 90% of the total budget (12 - 17 Billion Euros) is allocated to the first objective (Maroc 2008b). The majority of the interviews conducted in this study showed that the movement toward a cereals and export oriented agriculture is harmful for the long term resilience and sustainability of the valley because of its extremely high water consumption rates which may lead to a higher risk of crop failure and dependency on foreign markets fluctuations (interviews 2010-2012).

On the other hand, a date palm planting program consisting of five years with a budget of 26,431 MI USD⁷ (to cover a total area of 16,000 hectares and with 9,248 farmer beneficiaries) began in 2009. The project aims to improve the state of the date palm culture, which has been dramatically affected by droughts, floods, desertification rates, soil siltation, and the *Bayoud* (lethal mushroom) disease. Further, the project intends to upgrade the irrigation system over a length of 50 km to foster date palm cultivation by the introduction of 420 Bayoud disease resistant *plants*, to clean the tufts of 155,000 palm trees, promote small scale irrigated agriculture and to train farmers in terms of productivity and product enhancement with reference to such production system. As of 2012, the beneficiary oases are Ktawa (M'hamid), Ternata (Fezouata) and Tenzouline (Mazguita) (Fig 2).

In addition, the coexistence and synergisms between watermelon crops, new foreign cereal markets and date palm tree plantings all contributing to the microclimate of the oases, should reduce the conflicts over the regional water flow and use in an integrated way.

4.5 Tourism for desertification: “driver of” or potential solution?

While these drought events were negatively impacting vegetation, wildlife and the agricultural sector, the desert tourism sector was growing fast (Ait Hamza et al. 2009). Foreign visitors are attracted by the Ouarzazate growth of the American cinema industry, who had invested in the city by building one of the largest movie studios in Africa. Becoming a famous filmmaking location, Ouarzazate grew during the recent decades with an annual population growth of 3.3 % between 1994 and 2004 (Schulz and Judex 2008) and with an intention of providing 20.000 beds by 2010⁸ from just the 4524 beds in 1998. Zagora, a southern and second major city, also started to benefit from tourism, as did Mhamid (the last

⁷ It is funded through a partnership between the Ministry of Agriculture, the Hassan II Fund for Economic and Social Development and the Millenium Challenge Account (MCA).

⁸ Due to the global financial markets crisis from 2008 those numbers remains just wishes, and in 2010 the total bed numbers in Ouarzazate was stimated in 7.685 (Ministère du Tourisme et de l'Artesanat 2010)

oasis), which found tourism to provide economic survival opportunities after the most severe droughts. Furthermore, the nomads forced to settle in communities during the Sand War found a new source of income working as desert guides for tourists (interviews, 2010-2012).

Although the growing tourism sector was fast becoming a solution to the environmental crisis, the water consumption for tourist purposes increased significantly, contributing to further water scarcity and groundwater (and soil) salinization in the southern oases (Casciarri 2003), as a result of upstream water extraction. The ambitious project in the '90s by the European Lions Club to build the "Royal Golf" and "El Ahbab" five star hotels in Ouarzazate, taking advantage of the Mansour Al-Dhabi reservoir freshwater, illustrate the unintegrated and irresponsible approach to regional water management. Looking at the Drinkable Water Office database, Ouarzazat hotels alone reached 40% of the total urban water consumption (Office National de L'eau Potable 2010).

The highest star rating hotels may have higher water consumption, but these hotels have the greatest potential to build more sustainable options of incorporating water saving principles (storage, filtering and re-use strategies) once they become conscious about water scarcity. After the failure of Royal Golf as a result of the highly saline water used to irrigate the golf course, many building operators, mainly in the southern oases, started to incorporate water saving principles in their hotels. One example is the filtering and reuse of the water from the swimming pools for agriculture during dryer seasons (Interviews 2012). Another driver of change is how tourism and social networks have provided oasis nomads working in this new market with essential tools for coping with environmental crisis and desertification. These tools include sharing knowledge through social networks to raise awareness about desertification. For example, a local Bedouin camp in M'hamid (see Fig 4) started building sustainable water storage-filtering and reusing infrastructure in their camp in order to demonstrate that it is possible to sustainably manage tourist and farming in the middle of the desert.

- INSERT FIG 4
-

As illustrated in the pictures (Fig 4), Taragalte Bedouin camp has been constructed using a self made integrated water management structure, composed by well (functioning thanks to one solar photovoltaic panel) - water storage tank – toilets – underground natural filter – and a small farm from which they obtain some products for tourist consumption. The camp also began a tamarisk planting project in 2007, thanks to the collaboration with the Sahara Roots, a Dutch association which involves children living in the area to raise awareness among the new generations about how to cope with wind erosion, desertification and to create shade. The tamarisk tree project wants to demonstrate that the best way to fight desertification is not by building hard barriers (as illustrated in fig 4), a short term strategy resulting in the barriers becoming sand dunes themselves, but by planting highly drought resistant plants that are tolerant to the alkaline-saline

soils. In a few years, these tree plantings can significantly contribute to decreasing soil desertification thanks to plant roots and microclimate (Hebly and Hebly 2010). On one hand, tourism may constitute a consumer of the limited water resources, but on the other hand, it represents a tool and opportunity to demonstrate and build a new social-ecological equilibrium based on the sustainable use of the scarce resource. This is a small scale example of how to build resilience by enhancing skills, differentiating incomes and providing options for survival in a sustainable way.

5. Conclusions

The resilience of the Drâa valley population was mainly due to their flexible lifestyles (temporal migration in case of droughts) (Rachik 2007), a deep local environmental knowledge (respect for ecological thresholds), a multi resource economy and a common participative resource management (Casciarri 2006; Breuer 2007). These strategies conferred long term sustainability to the regional social-ecological system for centuries. Since 1972, centralized command and control practices regarding water management have resulted in the transformation of the cenentary, fragile but resilient, regional equilibrium (Casciarri 2003). Different strategies to droughts and increasing desertification rates have focused adaptation almost exclusively on short-term (resilience) solutions. These new centralized solutions, and local patterns of development (mainly energy, agriculture and tourism), are dependent on top-down, non-participative decisions, and on global markets fluctuations. The increasingly unsustainable uses of water upstream in the valley, fostering the role of city upon the regional chain of oases, do not reflect the need for water by the southern oasis. The region social-ecological equilibrium, and its sustainability, is in check.

The sustainability of CC adaptation strategies should recognize the elements for long term resilience of the regional social-ecological system. These elements are i) rooted in a balanced development of urban and rural systems across the region ii) the adoption of better adapted crops that are drought and salt tolerant, contributing to local food production, security and oases conservation (Thomas et al. 2007) and iii) the adoption of decentralized and integrated water and energy management (Campell et al., 2006), building capacities andempowering local people.

Sustainable adaptations to CC, in order to increase dryland resilience, require improving or at least maintaining the whole regional ecosystem functions and services. On the contrary, short term speculations built around external markets may decrease both ecological (because of possible overexplotations) and social (because the dependency from external resources) resilience, resulting in an unsustainable pattern of adaptation and development.

Figure captions

Fig 1. World drylands and Drâa Valley oases geographical context.

Source: from the authors, 2012.

Fig 2. Drâa Valley oases chain structure

Source: from the authors, 2012.

Fig 3. *Tiouine* (under construction) and *Mansour Eddahbi* (existing from 1972) dams.

Source from the authors, 2012.

Fig 4. Mhamid oasis structure ad Taragalte camp.

Source: from the authors, photos from Lorenzo Chelleri, 2012.

Tab 1: Number of animals in the Drâa region from 1980 to 2003 compared with water flows from Mansour Eddahbi dam.

Source: from the authors after Heidecke and Roth 2008, data taken from ORMVAO, 1980-2003 and DRPE, 2004.

Tab 2: Watermelons production rates in the province of Zagora

Source: ORMVAO (2013)

FIGURES

Fig 1

Fig 2

Fig 3

Fig 4

Tab 1

Tab 2

	2010	2011	2012	2013
<i>Watermelon farming area (ha)</i>	150	450	670	1130
<i>Watermelon Production (quintals)</i>	77650	240000	ND	ND

References

- Adger, W. Neil, Brown, Katrina, Nelson, Donald, Berkes, Firket, Eakin, Hallie, Folke, Carl, Galvin, Kathleen, Goulden, Gunderson, Lance, O'Brien, Karen, Ruitenbeek, Jack and Tompkins, Emma, Resilience Implications of Policy Responses to Climate Change, *WIREs Climate Change*, no. 2 (2011): 757-766
- Ait Hamza, Mohamed, Brahim, El Faskaoui and Fermin, Alfons, *Migration and environmental change in Morocco: The case of rural oasis villages in the Middle Drâa Valley*, *EACH-FOR Environmental Change and Forced Migration Scenarios*, Deliverable reference number and title: D 2.5.2.3 Morocco Case Study Report, (2009).
- Badraoui, M., Agbani, M. and Soudi, B., "Evolution de la qualité des sols sous mise en valeur intensive au Maroc." In *Séminaire 'Intensification agricole et qualité des sols et des eaux*, Rabat, 2-3 Novembre, (2000).
- Bakkoury, Mustafa, "Plan solaire Marocain: Un projet intégré et structurant" MASEN - Moroccan Agency for Solar Energy, (2010).
- Baran, Paul, *On distributed Communications: Introduction to Distributed Communication Network*, Santa Monica, California, RAND Corporation, (1964).
- Beaumont, Peter, *Drylands: Environment Management and Development*. London & New York, Routledge, (1989).
- Belgian Development Agency and Office National de L'eau Potable, *BTC and Assainissement liquide des villes de Zagora et de Tinghir - Ass Zagora Et Tinghir*, Maroc Projet 2008-2013, (2009).
- Ben Mohammadi A., Ben Mohammadi L., Ballais, J.L., Riser, J., *Analyse des interrelations anthropiques et naturelles: leur impact sur la recrudescence des phénomènes d'ensablement et de désertification du sud-est du Maroc (vallée de Drâa et vallée de Ziz)*, *Sécheresse* 11, (2000): 297-308.
- BioNomaD, "Projet de Conservation de La Biodiversité par la Transhumance dans le Versant Sud du Haut Atlas." Mor/99/G33/A/1G/99 - Ramsar site no. 1482, (2008).
- Biswas, Asit K., *Integrated Water Resources Management: A Reassment*, *Water International* 29, no. 2 (2004): 248-256.
- Breuer, Ingo, "Livelihood security and mobility in the high atlas mountains." In *Pastoral Morocco: Globalizing Scapes of Mobility and Insecurity*, edited by Gertel, Jörg and Breuer, Ingo, Reichert, Wiesbaden, (2007).
- Bunderministerium für Umwelt, Naturschutz und Reaktorsicherheit (Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety),

“Current press Releases”, no. 165/11, 15.11.2011

Casciarri, Barbara, “Coping with shrinking spaces: The Ait Unzar Pastoralists of south-eastern Morocco.” In *Nomadic societies in the Middle East and North Africa: entering the 21st century*, edited by D. Chatty. Leiden: Brill, (2006).

Casciarri, Barbara, “Rare Resources and Environmental Crises: Notes on Water Management among the Aït Unzâr Pastoralists in South-Eastern Morocco.” *Nomadic Peoples*, 7(1) (2003): 177-86

Davis, Kevis Diana, “Indigenous knowledge and desertification debate: problematising expert knowledge in North Africa.” *Geoforum*, 26 (2005): 509-524

Davis, Kevis Diana, “Neoliberalism, environmentalism, and agricultural restructuring in Morocco.” *Geographical Journal*, (2006): 172 88-105.

Direction de la Recherche et de la Planification de l’Eau, DRPE, 2004.

Dregne, Harold E., “Combating desertification: evaluation of progress.” *Environmental Conservation* 11, no. 2 (1984): 115-121

El Moudden, Saloua, “Impact du prélèvement du bois de feu sur les parcours steppiques cas d'Ighil n'Mgoun, province de Ouarzazate” (Thesis/Dissertation at Institut agronomique et veterinaire Hassan II, 2004): 138.

Faouzi, Ali, *Distribution de l'eau dans le Drâa Moyen, Office régional de mise en Valeur Agricole de Ouarzazate*, Ouarzazate: Morocco, (1986).

Food and Agriculture Organization, FAO National Study on Date Palm Irrigation and Associated Crops in the Kingdom of Morocco. Rome: Food and Agriculture Organization, (2006).

Food and Agriculture Organization, FAO Workshop on “Irrigation of Date Palm and Associated Crops”, Damascus, Syrian Arab Republic, 27-30 May, 2007. Rome: Food and Agriculture Organization, (2008).

Glantz, Michael and Orlovsky, Nicolai, “Desertification: a review of the concept.” *Desertification Control Bulletin* 9, (1983): 15–22.

Hebly, Adriaan and Hebly, Wanda, Report Treeplanting Oued Mahia – M’Hamid (South-Morocco), the Sahara-Roots Foundation, (2010).

Heidecke, Claudia and Roth, Andreas, “Drought Effects on Livestock Husbandry” in *IMPETUS Atlas Morocco. Research Results 2000–2007. 3rd Edition*, edited by Schulz, Oliver and Judex, Michael, Department of Geography, University of Bonn, Germany, (2008).

Heidecke, Claudia, Kuhn, Arnim, Liebelt, Claudia, “Hydro-economic processes and institutions in Southern Morocco,” in *Impacts of Global Change on the Hydrological Cycle in West and Northwest Africa*, edited by Speth, Peter, Christoph, Michael and Dieckrüger, Bernd. Heidelberg, Germany: Springer, (2008).

Herrmann, Stefanie M., Hutchinson, Charles F., “The changing debate contexts of the desertification debate.” *Journal of Arid Environments* 63, (2005): 538–555

Jeffrey, Paul and Gearey, Mary, “Integrated water resources management: Lost on the road from ambition to realisation?.” *Water Science and Technology*, 53, no. 1 (2006): 1-8.

Jellouli, D., Outabhit, H., “Effets sur l’environnement induits par l’édification du bradage Mansour Ed-Dahbi en vue de l’irrigation du périmètre du Draa Moyen, Environnement et développement.” In *Proceedings of 14th International Congress on Irrigation and Drainage*, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, 29 April-4 May, (1990).

Lankford, Bruce and Cour, Julien, “From Integrated to Adaptive: A New Framework for Water Resources Management of River Basins.” In *Proceedings of the East Africa River Basin Management Conference*, Morogoro, Tanzania, 7-9 March, (2005).

Lybbert, Travis J., Kusunose, Yoko, Magnan, Nicholas, and Fadlaoui, Abdelaziz, “Drought Risk and Drought Response in Morocco: Vulnerability, Risk Perceptions and Drought Coping among Rainfed Cereal Farmers.” In *AAEA & ACCI Joint Annual Meeting, Agricultural & Applied Economics Association*, Milwaukee, Wisconsin, July 26-29, (2009).

Mainguet, Monique and Da Silva, Graziano, “Desertification and Drylands Development: What can be done?.” *Land Degradation and Development* 9, (1998): 375-382.

Mainguet, Monique, “Lutte contre l'ensablement des palmeraies et des oasis du Sud marocain”, Rapport FAO, (1979): 58.

Mainguet, Monique, *L'Homme et la Secheresse*, Masson, Paris, (1995).

Maroc, “Études de faisabilité, la conception, l’évaluation environnementale et sociale et appui à l'exécution et à la supervision du Projet dans les zones irriguées (PMH et Oasis)”, (2009).

Maroc, “Le Plan Maroc Vert: Plan Agricole Région Souss-Massa Drâa” (2008a). <http://www.ada.gov.ma/documentation/documentation-agence-developpement-agricole-maroc.php>

Maroc, “Plan Maroc Vert: Premières perspectives de la stratégie agricole” (Meknès, 2008b). www.vulgarization.net/plan_maroc_vert.pdf

Maroc, “Programme d’action national de lutte contre la desertification document principal. ministere de l'agriculture, du developpement rural et des eaux et forets”, (2001).

Maroc, “Synthèse de l’étude: Evaluation du changement climatique futur au niveau des zones oasiennes marocaines,” PACC Oasis project, (2011).

- Maroc, Chambre des représentants, “Loi n 10-95 sur l'Eau”, 15 juillet 1995.
- Martín Bravo, Elena and Salgado Ybern, Beatriz, *El Sector del Agua en Marruecos*, Instituto Español de Comercio Exterior – Oficina Económica y Comercial de la Embajada de España en Rabat, (2008).
- Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, *Ecosystems and human well-being: Desertification synthesis*. World Resources Institute, Washington, D.C., Island Press, (2005).
- Ministère de l’Agriculture, du Développement rural et des Eaux et Forêts, *MADREF Programme d’action nationale de lutte contre la desertification*. (2001): 134.
- Ministère de l’Energie, des Mines, de l’Eau et de l’Environnement, “MADREF Loi n° 57-09 portant création de la Société Moroccan Agency for Solar Energy”, (2010).
- Ministère de l’Energie, des Mines, de l’Eau et de l’Environnement, Département de l’Environnement, *Projet 2009-2012* (2009).
- Ministere de l’Energie, des Mines, de l’Eau et de l’Environnement, Département de l’Eau, *Ressources en Eau per Bassin: Draa*, 2012. http://www.water.gov.ma/index.cfm?gen=true&id=13&ID_PAGE=37
- Ministère du Tourisme et de l’Artisanat, Département du tourisme, “Le tourisme en chiffres 2010”, BMCE Bank, (2010a).
- Monje, Beatriz Cerezo, Ramirez, Rosalva Espino, Roig, Cristina Silvera, “Le Secteur de l’Eau au Maroc,” *Programa Cooperacion Transfronteriza Espana-Fronteras Exteriores*, (2011).
- Nicholson, S. E., Tucker, C. J., Ba, M.B., “Desertification, drought, and surface vegetation: an example from the West African Sahel.” *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society* 79, (1998): 815-829.
- Office Régional de Mise en Valeur Agricole d’Ouarzazate, ORMVAO, *Bilan des activités de 2013 de l’office régional de mise en valeur agricole de Ouarzazate*, Ouarzazate, (2013).
- Ouassou, A., Ameziane, T., Belghiti, M., Ziyad, A. and Belhamd, A., “Morocco.” *Options Méditerranéennes - Series B*, no. 51 (2005).
- Platt, Stephan, *Current Development of the Population in the Provinces of Ouarzazate and Zagora in IMPETUS Atlas Morocco. Research Results 2000–2007. 3rd Edition*, edited by Schulz, Oliver and Judex, Michael, Department of Geography, University of Bonn, Germany, (2008).
- Rachik, Hassan, *Nomads: But how? In Pastoral Morocco: Globalizing Scapes of Mobility and Insecurity*, edited by Gertel, Jörg and Breuer, Ingo, Reichert, Wiesbaden, (2007).
- Rademacher, Christina, *Traditional and Modern Irrigation in Ouled Yaoub in IMPETUS Atlas Morocco. Research Results 2000–2007 3rd Edition*, edited by

Schulz, Oliver and Judex, Michael, Department of Geography, University of Bonn, Germany, (2008).

Schulz, Oliver and Judex, Michael (edited by), *IMPETUS Atlas Morocco. Research Results 2000–2007, 3rd Edition*, Department of Geography, University of Bonn, Germany, (2008).

Spooner, B., “The paradoxes of desertification.” *Desertification Control Bulletin* 15, (1987): 40-45.

Stebbing, Edward Percy, “The encroaching Sahara: the threat to the West African colonies.” *Geographical Journal* 85, (1935): 506–519.

Tazi, Mohamed, “Problematique de l’economie de l’eau d’irrigation dans la Zone d’action de l’ORMVA de Ouarzazate.” *Revue HTE* 141, (2008): 7-10.

The Club of Rome, “Red Paper. An Overview of the Desertec Concept”, (2011).

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, IPCC, 2013: *Climate Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* [Stocker, T. F., D. Qin, G.-K. Plattner, M. Tignor, S. K. Allen, J. Boschung, A. Nauels, Y. Xia, V. Bex and P. M. Midgley (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, in press

Thomas, Richard J., de Pauw, Eddy, Manzoor Qadir, Amri, Ahmed, Pala, Mustapha, Yahyaoui, Amor, El-Bouhssini, Mustapha, Baum, Michael, Iñiguez, Luiz, and Shideed, Kamel, “Increasing the Resilience of Dryland Agro-ecosystems to Climate Change.” *SAT eJournal* 4, no. 1 (2007): 1-37.

Touchan, Ramzi, Anchukaitis, Kevin J., Meko, David, Attalah, Said, Baisan, Christopher, Aloui, Ali. “Long term context for recent drought in northwestern Africa.” *Geophysical Research Letters* 58, (2008).

United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification, UNCCD What is desertification?, 2003. <http://www.unccd.int/knowledge/faq.php>.

Zainabi, Ahmed, “La Vallée du Dra: Developement Alternatif et Action Communautaire,” Background paper WDR, (2003).]